

One Day National Level Seminar On Contemporary Discourses in English Studies

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 1

Month : July

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-2645

Impact Factor: 4.110

Citation:

Sinthu, R. "One Day National Level Seminar On Contemporary Discourses in English Studies." *Shanlax International Journal of English*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 158–61.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3457057>

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Introduction

Amish Tripathi an Indian English author well known for the series of 7 books under the title of Shiva Trilogy (3 books), Ram Chandra Series (currently 3 books), and Immortal India (non-fiction). The popularity he gained can be realised by the awards and nominations given to him. He has been awarded "Society Young Achievers Award for Literature in 2013" in the year when his last book to the trilogy has been released. The writers such as Cheton Bhagat, Priti Shenoy, Amish Tripathi and so.... Mainly focus in day to day lives problems in a creative manner. There are few more authors such as Ashok Banker and Amish Tripathi follows a mythological fiction pattern. They club mythology and day to day life pattern to provide morals and values to people mind set in current age. "50 Most influential Young Indians" nomination contained his name in the year of 2015 and "Intellectual Property – Inspiration Icon of the year of the year 2018" was given to him. In his young age Tripathi was an Atheist, but he returned back to being Trust in action and Have Faith in God. Throughout the book the main perception is that "The Action of a Man, Turns Him into God".

Traditional Vs Morden: Cultural studies

Life style

The protagonist Shiva is a barbarian from a tribe called Guna tribe, North India in Tibet. The stages he goes through is the value education throughout the book. The drastic change of a barbarian life to a life of a Saviour of different races believing in one person "The Neelkanth" is portrayed. This change from man to a Saviour of races with morals and self believes made the man to be reverted as a God, The Legend who we now call "Lord Shiva".

There were three different kind of races focused on this book. The first is Suryavanshi, the followers of Lord Ram, one of the greatest King to ever live and rule with perfection. Suryavsnshi. Suryavanshi's believe in Neelkanth, the Saviour. The Suryavanshi people were faced with crises over a river which takes water to the

whole kingdom. They strongly believe that the reason for extinction of River Saraswathi is because of the Evil Chandravanshi's who have waged war from the beginning. The present Meluhan King-King Daksha has invited Shiva's tribe to Meluha, he is in a quest on finding the Neelkanth, their Saviour. The Guna tribe people were impressed with the extravagant way of life in Meluha. The tribe people were treated warmly and are given some medicines for purification of 'their disease, since Meluha is a disease free kingdom'. But in the night the tribal people had severe fever and sweating except Shiva, whose throat had turned blue in color. Every person rejoiced in Meluha because their Saviour Neelkanth finally came when the need for the eradication of evil is required.

Analysation

Present era Comparison

The first book speaks of a confused man's life as a local person (Barbarian – person with low morals). Considering Shiva as a man with no job or no ambition in life kind of person, we can easily understand the book in completely a modern era reflector. Consider Shiva as a local gangster, who is taken to another place where he learns the value of life and morals. This kind of transformation from one personality to another is a daily occurrence in many people's life in different areas. We all have witnessed these change in our life. Some may have witnessed in career, some in personal life, some in relationship there are many.... One person's belief on someone may have made that someone a singer, one person's experience might have created a writer, and a dad's wish might have created a doctor or an entrepreneur. The same was the situation to Shiva, the Meluhan's trust on Shiva as their Saviour, The Neelkanth, brought changes which made him achieve greater level of admiration. This admiration provided him the status of "Lord Shiva".

Cast and Community

After a long travel from Meluha to the capital city of Meluha, Devagiri, Shiva meets the Daksha-the Meluhan King. While staying there Shiva encounters various cultural etiquettes. For instance, every Meluhan wears simple white cloths called as Angavastra and Dothi. Both Men and Women wear a small white cloth tied and wrapped in a Meluhan style, which they call Dothi. And Women also wear a simple white cloth tied around their chest as blouse, while another white cloth is draped on their shoulders called as Angavastra. And also they wore two amulets around their right arm, and a pendant on a gold chain around their neck. When Shiva enquires his comrade Nandi about the amulets and pendant, Nandi explains it as

“ ‘Can you tell me the significance of your jewellery or is that also a state secret?’ teased Shiva. ‘Of course I can, my Lord.’ Replied Nandi earnestly. He pointed at the first amulet that had been tied around his massive arm with a Silky gold thread, ‘This is the amulet which represents my caste. The lines drawn on it symbolize the shoulder of the Paramatma, the almighty. This means that I am Kshatriya.’ ” (PDF. 32 TIOM)

Nandhi also describes that the second amulet represents his/her chosen tribe. Each tribe has to take the job of his/her parents after turning twenty-five. Brahmins choose from birds representing their vulnerability whereas Kshatriyas choose from animals representing valour and dignity. Vaishyas choose from flowers depicting their job of producers or farmers or businessmen. The last civilised people were called as Sundras were to choose from fishes. This allocation of tribe is what describes the person's value in that society. For instance; Nandhi is a Kshatriya, and his amulet has a bull embedded in it. He is a warrior captain of a part of Meluhan army.

Analyzation

Present era Comparison

We people have cast and community system. This is exactly what those amulets and pendants

describe. In present days we collaborate our work with other cast people, but there are still some society people who would not at certain works or places allow other cast people, or community people to mingle with them. Still in village areas, there were some group of people who would not allow certain community people to do some works, such as fetching drinking water or touching their washed dresses and so on. But while Nandi explains about cast system depending on the chosen tribe he explains that the person has to his/her own tribe and the symbol according to their capacity. The basic thing explained is that the person has to choose a work or a job that fits them. Choosing a job which is an overload for their capacity will bring that person embarrassment. Because if we take a job and we know it is out of our capacity but we still wants to do it might bring shame on us, if we did not complete it.

The theme is that person who has the capacity to do certain jobs should do that jobs. Because they have the tendency to do it. Their passion, their knowledge, and their interest everything plays a vital role in a man's life and career. For instance; the antagonist in the film *The Dark Knight*, Heath Ledger, was cast as an antagonist before even the script was written. His passion as a Legendry Joker, gave him complete recognition as *The Joker* to everyone. But least of us know that he was given the role of *The Batman* in *The Batman* movie.

Vikrama and Naga

While staying there Shiva met Sati, the Meluhan Princess. He fell head over heels in love with her, in the first sight. Shiva courts Sati but she kept rejecting and refusing his proposal. Later on Shiva finds that Sati was a Vikrama, an untouchable person in this life because they were punished for the sins of their previous birth. When Shiva came to know about this Vikrama People, he was furious. A person is declared Vikrama according to various believes of Meluhan people. A women is considered a Vikrama if her husband dies an unexpected death or that her child has any deformities or is of still birth. And a man is considered a Vikrama if he has any sudden fatal disease or any physical deformities in an unusual way. Shiva enquires Nandi about the believes of Meluhans over Vikrama and the revelation were more than a civilized belief. It utterly barbaric.

The Vikrama women has to do purification prayer every month for forgiveness from Lord Agni, the Lord of Fire and Purification. And likewise the Vikrama men have another kind of mandatory Pooja to do every month. These people were not allowed to marry anyone again, or touch anyone other than their family members. When Shiva learned that Sati is a Vikrama he gets furious because he believes that, a person is considered sinful because of his/her action and not because of their life/fate or birth.

“ ‘They are not allowed to marry since they may poison others with their bad fate..... There are many other conditions as well as that I am not completely aware of it.....’ - says Nandi to Shiva.” Pp- 93 TIOM

“ ‘Who decided that Vikrama people had committed sins in their previous birth?’ ‘Their own karma, my Lord’, said Nandi” Pp- 93 TIOM

The Nagas were a cursed race of people who were born with deformities. These people face the worse kind of rejection than Vikrama people. The Nagas were disowned by their family and are send to a place called Dandak Forest where rest of the disowned Nagas reside. This Dandak forest is a dense and deceitful forest, where with every step a non-resident of that forest (i.e. Non-Nagas) has to be careful. If and if they do not want to die a miserable death. The prime characters were Ganesh, the first son of Sati and Kali, the twin sister of Sati. Both were disowned by the King Daksha, because of their deformities. Even more Daksha had hidden the truth about Sati's first child saying that her first child was of still birth.

Analyzation

Present era Comparison

Vikrama

We still have, at some remote areas, even globally, the practices of untouchability. Those people were not allowed to touch anyone and we even had the practice of ‘Sati’ in India. Slowly the practice has been abolished and the reformation has been done. The practice of Sati, is what mentioned as the Vikrama people. The ill fate people who have been given no recognition even though the deformities or the birth right is not their fault. They were viewed as an abomination, where literally treated with disgrace. Though the practice was not present in this 3-4 decades, the aftermath of the reformation has not been completely forgotten. These kind of reformation has happened in this novel too.

Nagas

From the second novel these outcast people’s society were clearly portrayed. The children born in some families were left in foresters care. These kind of act is what the Nagas have suffered. Parents knowingly, or sometimes ignorant of their possibility to take care of their children leave them abandoned. These kind of act was in present days are common too.

Conclusion

Tripathi believes that “Myths are nothing but jumbled memories of a true past. A past buried under mounds of earth and ignorance.” The notes on modern and mythological twist is the highest point of combination. To teach morals people normally will state legends and mythological heroes. But Tripathi have produced what modern society needs in culture values and moral teachings. The Essence of philosophy in Amish’s novels is as quoted by Sneha Josie in Analysis of Shiva Trilogy- The Immortals of Meluha “Vice and virtue are inevitable. Instead of making them wage war against each other Amish has handled this concept effectively by illustrating the enigmatic quality of good and evil.”

Amish has provided with the main concept as ‘good and evil has to maintain a healthy amount of relationship with each other. The people on both sides has to understand the value of each other and try to move with their given/ provided works/ missions. If one tries to surpass the other, it tips the scales and the balance of nature is distorted.’

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